

SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN VILLAGE LIONS NAGAR, KHAJERLI (A MICRO LEVEL ANALYSIS)

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Abstract:

The present paper is an attempt to evaluate the socio-economic development in village Lions Nagar, Khajerli at ward level. Secondary data is collected from census of India, literatures, historical records, old-age population etc. The primary data has been gathered through a census household survey carried on 20 – 22 September, 2016 in the village. In total 170 households were covered using structured questionnaires. The composite index of socio-economic development of 15 variables is calculated with the help of Z score. The six numerically dominant castes are living in segregated residential pattern in the respective social space and wards indicating socio-religio dominance model in the village. The study indicates that the habitats or wards of upper castes are better developed as compared to lower castes in the village.

Statement of the Problem:

Socio-economic development is the process of social and economic development in the society. It includes the level of economic growth, education, health services, status of women, and quality of housing, distribution of goods and services, and access to communication. The progress of socio-economic development in India is not uniform (Das, A. 1999: 313). Socio-economic disparity on the basis of caste has been common in rural as well as urban settlement for generations in India. Education has been valued as an engine of social change but it was in access of only a few selected sections of the society. These naturally broaden the gap in socio-economic development among population belonging to various castes. (Kulkarni, 2002:5). After independence in India, democratic set-ups are redesigning socio-economic development particularly in rural areas.

Study Area:

The village "Lions Nagar - Khajerli" a typical village in arid region of Jodhpur district of Rajasthan located at 29°09' 35" North latitude and 73°09' 25" East longitude (fig.1).

Objectives of Study:

The present study seeks;

- ✓ To evaluate the socio-economic development at ward level.
- ✓ To examine the relationship between social space occupation (castes) and level of socio-economic development.

Research Questions:

- ✓ Is there any disparity in the level of socio-economic development at ward level?
- ✓ What is the relationship between social space occupation (castes) and level of socio-economic development?

Data Base and Methodology:

The present study based on both published and unpublished data. Secondary data is collected from census of India, literatures, historical records, old-age population etc. The primary data has been gathered through a census household survey carried on 20 – 22 September, 2016 in the village. In total 170 households were covered using structured questionnaires. The ward map (Fig. 2) and social morphological map of the village is prepared using Google image with supportive primary informations. The composite index of socio-economic development of 15 variables is calculated with the help of Z score;

$$Z = \frac{x - \bar{x}}{S.D.}$$

Whereas, Z = Z-score, X is value of indicators, \bar{x} mean of indicators and S.D. is standard deviation. Status of Wards based on average Z-score i.e. divided composite Z-score by variables: positive Z-score means developed while negative Z- score means backward wards in the map.

Socio-Economic Analysis:

In 1978, the region of Khajerli Kalan experienced heavy rainfall. Due to which, the low lying Kachha-inhabited houses of said village was flooded and destroyed. Therefore, the Lions Club, Jodhpur with the help of administration rehabilitated the displaced poor people on the cost free land of common property resource of said village and inhabited in the form of tent. With the passage of time, they developed planned residential area for SC / low income people. While BC / GEN / middle to high income people purchased their plots and constructed the houses on themselves resources. As a resulted, the people of different castes resided here and presently, it is a small settlement, namely “Lions Nagar” of about 170 households.

Bishnoi is the dominating caste in the village accounting for 21.17 percent of total households. In total, more than 13 castes are observed in the village. About 74.72 percent households belong to Hindu religion followed by Bishnoi (21.17 percent) and Muslim (4.11 percent). The six numerically dominant castes are living

in segregated residential pattern in the respective social space and wards indicating socio-religio dominance model in the village (Fig.3).

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

The surveyed population of the village is 978 in the village. The proportion of males and female are about 53.58 and 46.42 percent. About 47.52 percent population of the village is literate with significant variations between male and female i.e. 63.83 percent and 36.16 percent respectively. Three-fourth percent (75.13 percent) of literates are observed as literates below matric level of education. There are 866 females per thousand males in the village. The work participation rate (main worker) in the village is about 32.82 percent. About 78 percent workers are engaged in primary economic activities. The per capita monthly income in the village is i.e. about Rs.13371.00. About 42.35 percent households are living in Pucca houses. About 64.71 percent households of the village have separate kitchen in their house. It is a good indication that 57.64 percent households have LPG connection facilities in their Kitchen. About 83.53 percent households have water tap facility in their own house. It is not good sign that only 25.88 percent households have toilet facility in their own house. About 50.59 percent households have T.V. in their house. It is good that 77.06 percent households have mobile facility.

Composite index of Socio-Economic Development:

Fifteen variables of socio-economic development have been included to develop the ward wise composite index of Socio-Economic Development such as total population, child sex ratio, overall sex ratio, literacy, female literacy, non-agricultural and labour workers, per capita monthly income, pucca house, room density, LPG connection, separate kitchen, water tap, toilet facility, TV and mobile facilities. Fig. 4 reveals the spatial variations in level of socio-economic development at ward level in the village. Ward 1, 2 and 6 are observed as developed. These wards are dominantly inhabited by Bishnoi community included in general caste while ward 3, 4 and 5 are observed as backward habitats. These are dominantly inhabited by backward and scheduled castes.

Conclusion:

The study answers the raised research questions that there exist spatial variation in level of development at ward level and the habitats or wards of general castes are better developed as compared to scheduled and backward castes in the village.

Reference:

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